

EFFECT OF THE REINFORCING SiC, Cg AND GR PARTICLES ON THE STRUCTURE AND PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE PISTONS BASED ON AlSi7Mg2Sr0.03 ALLOY

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Abstract

The study gives characteristics of the structure and properties of the composite pistons based on AlSi7Mg2Sr0.03 alloy with different proportional content of SiC, Cg and GR particles, cast under industrial conditions. Samples taken from castings were also tested for the mechanical properties in static tensile test, and additionally measurements of Young's modulus (E) were performed and testing of mechanical properties in a compression test at elevated temperature.

Regardless of the type and content of particles, small differences were observed to exist in the properties of the composite pistons. A common feature of the examined castings was the stability of properties in the compression test up to a temperature of 250°C. Upon exceeding this temperature, the compressive yield strength and the strength in compression decreased. Pistons significantly differed in terms of the weight loss after the Taber abrasion test, which had a decisive influence on their functional properties. The smallest loss of weight was found in pistons containing 10% SiC, and 10% SiC + 10% GR.

1 INTRODUCTION

Products fabricated from composites based on aluminium alloys are increasingly used in transport [1,2]. Market demands from these products continuously improved quality, which means optimising their production [3,4], structure [5], properties (moreover tribological) [6,7] also in terms of cost.

The study gives characteristics of the structure and properties of the composite pistons based on AlSi7Mg2Sr0.03 alloy with different proportional content of SiC, Cg (glassy carbon) and GR (graphite) particles, cast under industrial conditions.

2 METHODOLOGY

Tests were carried out on composite pistons obtained by gravity casting at the Złotecki Ltd. Company [3,4]. To prepare a composite suspension, the AlSi7Mg base alloy was used. The alloy, after melting at 720°C, was refined with argon jet flowing at a rate of 2l/h. Modification of the chemical composition of alloy matrix was accomplished with AlMg25, AlSr master alloy (Table 1). For the composite reinforcing phase, particles of the following materials were selected: silicon carbide (SiC), glassy carbon (Cg), spherical graphite (GR), and a hybrid mixture of SiC/Cg and SiC/GR.

	Si	Fe	Cu	Mn	Mg	Ti	Sr	B
AlSi7Mg2Sr003	9.04	0.355	0.266	0.245	2.35	0.114	0.044	0.0011

Table 1: Chemical composition of AlSi7Mg2Sr003 alloy [wt%].

Pistons were cast from the following composites: AlSi7Mg2Sr0.03 with 5%SiC, 5%SiC+2%Cg, 10%SiC, 10%SiC+10%GR. To reveal the macrostructure, castings were cut through the gating system and riser. Then, specimens were cut out from the castings and metallographic sections were prepared. The composites were examined under an Olympus GX71 light microscope (LM). Strength testing in the static tensile test and compression test at temperatures of 20°C, 100°C, 200°C, 250°C, 300°C was carried out on an Instron 5582 - 100kN testing machine equipped with a temperature chamber operating in the temperature range from - 150°C to 350°C. Abrasion resistance tests were performed on a Taber Abraser 5155 device monitoring the loss in weight after 1000 and 5000 abrasion cycles on 10 samples of the selected material. Abrasion tests were done under the same conditions for all four series of composites.

3 TEST RESULTS

As a result of the conducted structure examinations, a uniform distribution of the reinforcing phases was confirmed in all the examined composite pistons (Fig. 1). In some areas of the sample, small conglomerates of particles are visible, inside which a few voids have occurred caused by particles detached and “falling out” during the preparation of metallographic section. In the case of hybrid composites, the flake particles of Cg were several times larger than the particles of SiC and relatively more dispersed in the matrix (Fig. 1b). Composites in which, in addition to SiC, also 10% GR was used showed a lower actual content of these particles (Fig. 1d). Although graphite particles introduced into the master alloy were of oval shapes, particles of this shape were not detected in the structure. Graphite in the AlSi7Mg2Sr0.03 matrix assumed the form of elongated particles with strongly developed phase boundary.

Figure1: The structure of composites based on AlSi7Mg2Sr0,03 reinforced with particles of: a) 5%SiC, b) 5%SiC+2%Cg, c)10%SiC, d) 10%SiC+10%GR.

The results of strength tests conducted on the hybrid composites were comparable though lower in values than those obtained for the starting material (Table 2). More pronounced differences were

observed only in Young's modulus (E). Samples of AlSi7Mg2Sr0,03 alloy showed similar levels of elastic modulus as a composite with 5% SiC + 2% Cg. In hybrid composite, comparable results may prove the lack of an effect of the 5% SiC + 2% Cg reinforcing phase content on the elastic modulus. In the case of composite containing 10%SiC+10%Cs as a reinforcing phase, the values of Young's modulus were by 10GPa higher than in the other two materials, which may indicate that in this case the presence of the reinforcing phase had some impact on the level of the composite elastic modulus.

Material	Rp _{0,2} [MPa]	Rm [MPa]	A [%]	E [GPa]
AlSi7Mg2Sr0.03	142±1,5	179±4,1	0,7±0,2	60,2±7,1
5%SiC+2%Cg	114 ±10	127 ±15	0,3 ±0,05	59,6 ±3,2
10%SiC+10%GR	114±4,0	117±3,1	–	71,3±7,3

Table 2: The results of strength testing and Young's modulus calculations for composites containing SiC, Cg and GR.

The yield stress was determined in a compression test at elevated temperature (Fig. 2). The results indicated very stable properties of the yield strength in the tested materials up to a temperature of 200°C. Above this temperature, the yield strength was gently decreasing for samples with 10% SiC and 10% SiC + 10% GR. In contrast, for other samples with 5% SiC and 5% SiC% + 2%Cg, the value of the yield stress was stable up to 250°C. Upon exceeding this temperature, the yield strength decreased to approx. 120MPa.

Figure: 2 The yield strength R_{p0,2} in compression vs temperature.

Taber abrasion tests involved comparison and calculation of differences in weight loss between the initial sample and sample after the test. The results have indicated that the material most resistant to abrasion was composite containing 10% SiC after both 1000 and 5000 abrasion cycles (Table 3). Equally good resistance had hybrid composites containing graphite and glassy carbon. The greatest loss in weight and also the lowest abrasion resistance among all the materials tested has revealed the composite containing 5% SiC.

Number of revolutions	5%SiC	10%SiC	5%SiC+2%Cg	10%SiC+10%GR
1000	16,76	5,33	13,11	11,54
5000	52,27	13,68	56,04	19,92

Table 3: Average weight loss [mg] in samples after the Taber abrasion test.

4 CONCLUSIONS:

As a result of the studies carried out it was concluded that:

1. The best functional properties, including structure and compressive strength, were obtained in the composite containing 10% SiC.
2. On the examined cross-sections of cast pistons, no major defects were observed; particles of the reinforcing phase showed a uniform distribution.
3. The structure of the composites was characterized by the presence of fine pores/voids resulting from poor embedding of particles, mainly the particles of SiC.
4. The phases of Cg and GR were evenly distributed in the structure. However, the shape of graphite did not resemble the shape of the granules introduced into the slurry. It had an elongated shape and strongly developed interface.
5. The resistance properties obtained in static tensile test were lower for the composite compared with the starting material. In contrast, the highest Young's modulus (E) was observed in the composite reinforced with 10% SiC + 10% Cg.
6. The yield strength in composites with higher content of the reinforcing phase particles was gently decreasing after reaching 200°C, while in composites with a lower content of the particles it revealed a drop above 250°C. The lowest yield strength had the composite containing 10% SiC + 10% GR.
7. The best wear resistance was obtained in the composite containing 10% SiC and 10% SiC + 10% GR.

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